

EXPLORING HOW PURPOSE-DRIVEN INNOVATION (PDI) LEADS TO SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS GROWTH IN MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES (MSEs): A QUALITATIVE CASE STUDY IN VIETNAM

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PURPOSE AND BACKGROUND

The relationship between purpose and innovation has garnered significant attention in business management and strategy. While innovation is widely acknowledged as crucial for sustaining competitive advantage, a clear sense of purpose can enhance business performance (Henderson, 2020). However, understanding how purpose-driven innovation (PDI) influences value creation and overall business performance remains an emerging area with considerable research potential. Previous studies suggest that integrating purpose with innovation can drive sustainable business growth, but there is a notable research gap regarding this relationship.

This study investigates the impact of PDI on fostering sustainable business growth, specifically through the execution of PDI projects. Grounded in the theoretical frameworks of Paradox Theory, Organizational Ambidexterity, and Dynamic Capabilities, this research aims to address the following questions: How does PDI facilitate organizational ambidexterity? What role do leadership, organizational culture, and strategic alignment with purpose play in achieving PDI? Initial findings suggest that top management commitment and organizational learning are crucial factors in balancing exploration and exploitation within innovation processes.

Rang Dong, a leading Vietnamese enterprise recognized for its purpose-aligned strategies, serves as a case study to illustrate how PDI fosters organizational ambidexterity and drives sustainable business growth (Grant, 2024). Rang Dong's

purpose-driven innovation projects focus on twin transformation, which emphasizes leveraging technological advancements and innovative practices to achieve sustainable development goals. This approach encourages companies to rethink and redesign their operational frameworks to be more sustainable and efficient. Furthermore, Rang Dong engages in open innovation, which involves systematically incorporating external knowledge and insights to accelerate internal innovation efforts while expanding market opportunities. By integrating diverse sources of knowledge, organizations can enhance their innovation capabilities and ensure that their offerings remain relevant in a rapidly changing market landscape. After nearly three decades of consistent growth, Rang Dong aims to achieve a revenue milestone of \$1 billion by 2030, positioning itself among the largest companies in Vietnam through its purpose-driven management philosophy.

Purpose-led strategies facilitate continuous innovation and adaptability by avoiding corporate myopia and ensuring stakeholder engagement. This balance appears essential for cultivating new, value-generating PDI projects. The research employs a qualitative case study methodology, which allows for an in-depth exploration of the context, processes, and impacts of PDI in micro and small enterprises (MSEs) in the Asia-Pacific region. Qualitative methods, including interviews and document analysis, provide insights into the lived experiences of participants and the organizational dynamics that influence innovation outcomes. This approach not only enriches the understanding of PDI but also highlights the complexities and interdependencies inherent in organizational change.

These early insights indicate that organizational ambidexterity is closely linked to the conception of PDI, strategic alignment with stakeholder value, and the creation of a supportive organizational culture within an open operating model. Initial findings further reveal that these dynamics are facilitated by top management commitment and enhanced through organizational learning. By utilizing a robust case study approach, this research bridges the gap between detailed qualitative analysis and the generation of actionable insights and practical applications.

Ultimately, this research contributes to the theoretical discourse on purpose, innovation, and purpose-driven innovation by demonstrating that organizations in developing countries like Vietnam can enhance value generation and improve business performance through the implementation of PDI. By integrating PDI projects into continuous business design via organizational ambidexterity, the study offers valuable managerial insights for medium-sized enterprises (MSEs) in Vietnam while suggesting future research directions, particularly through quantitative approaches..

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Grant, M. (2024). Purpose-driven innovation: A new paradigm for sustainable business growth. *Journal of Business Strategy*,
- Lee, S., Bansal, P., & Barbosa, A. M. (2023). Seeing beyond the here and now: How corporate purpose combats corporate myopia. *Strategy Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1287/stsc.2023.0183>

- Mendoza-Silva, A. (2021). Innovation capability: A systematic literature review. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 24(3), 707-734. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-09-2019-0263>.
- Henderson, R. (2020). Innovation in the 21st century: Architectural change, purpose, and the challenges of our time. *Management Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2020.374>.
- EY. (2018). How to attain purpose-led transformation. Ernst & Young Global